

METHODOLOGY FOR GENERATING AND VALIDATING MICROMODELS TO PREDICT FIBER-DIRECTION COMPRESSIVE FAILURE IN CFRPS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites (CFRPs) enable lightweight, strong, and durable structures for a wide range of engineering applications, including aerospace, automotive, biomedical, and civil systems. To accelerate material development and reduce certification costs, there is increasing reliance on modeling within Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME) frameworks. In recent years, micromodels have shown promise in predicting material allowables for structural quantification. However, the complex failure mechanisms of CFRPs—particularly fiber-direction compressive failure—continue to present challenges, especially when bridging microscale behavior with macroscale performance. Fiber-direction compressive failure, typically governed by fiber kinking due to initial fiber misalignment and shear instability, is a key limiting factor in the design of primary CFRP aircraft structures. While Representative Volume Element (RVE) models have advanced the understanding of fiber kinking, they often rely on idealized assumptions—such as uniaxial sine-wave misalignment—that do not capture the inherently random nature of CFRP microstructures and fiber architecture. Furthermore, experimental validation at the microscale remains limited.

To address these limitations, this work presents a novel computer graphics-based methodology for generating densely packed 3D micromodels with realistic, randomly distributed fibers and local 3D misalignments using the open-source software Blender. The generated models are first used in RVE simulations to investigate the effect of random misalignment on compressive strength. Comparisons with conventional RVEs using uniform and uniaxial misalignment highlight the limitations of oversimplified assumptions and underscore the importance of statistically representative geometries.

A thin four-point bend notched test specimen is also introduced as a proposed path toward experimental validation of micromodels for predicting fiber kinking. The specimen is designed to promote localized kinking and enable direct comparison with simulation results. The numerical model includes a homogenized global FE model and a locally embedded fiber-segmented micromodel to capture fiber kinking in the notch region.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer composites (CFRPs) enable lightweight, strong, and durable structures for a wide of range engineering applications, including aerospace, automotive, biomedical, and civil industries. To accelerate and reduce the cost of material design and qualification, as well as structural design, certification, and sustainment of advanced CFRPs parts, there has been a growing demand for greater reliance on modeling. In particular, recent years have seen significant progress in the development of micromodels for predicting material allowables that can be used for structural quantification. The advancement of such multiscale modeling capabilities has the potential to significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of composite part design within the framework of Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME) [1-3]. However, the complex failure mechanisms of CFRPs continue to pose significant challenges to modeling efforts, particularly when bridging the gap between microscale behavior and macroscale performance.

A key critical challenge is the development and validation of micromodels for predicting fiber-direction compressive failure. The fiber-direction compressive strength of unidirectional CFRPs is significantly lower than the tensile strength, with experimental data typically reporting a 30-40% reduction for intermediate modulus (IM) carbon fiber material systems [4-5]. This reduction is a limiting factor in the design of primary composite aircraft structures. Fiber-direction compressive failure in CFRPs is generally governed by the formation of fiber kinking, which can involve multiple interacting microscale mechanisms such as matrix yielding, fiber-matrix debonding, and fiber fracture.

Micromechanical finite element (FE) models, often based on Representative Volume Elements (RVEs), have been instrumental in improving the understanding of fiber kinking by incorporating explicit microstructural features such as fiber distribution and misalignment [6-9]. These models have proven valuable for estimating the compressive strength based on constituent properties [8-10]. However, most existing micromodels rely on idealized representations of fiber architecture, often assuming uniform, uniaxial sine-wave fiber misalignment to initiate shear instability and formation of fiber kinking. These simplifications neglect the inherent stochastic nature of fiber misalignment that arises from manufacturing variability, limiting their predictive capability.

The synthetic generation of realistic micromodels with highly packed non-intersecting fibers with spatially varying, random 3D misalignment presents significant geometric and meshing challenges. To address this challenge, this work introduces a new methodology that leverages Blender—an open-source computer graphics software—to rapidly generate densely packed three-dimensional (3D) fiber distributions with stochastic misalignment and high fiber counts. The approach is fully automated using Python scripting and relies on Blender’s rigid body simulation engine, allowing the user to specify key input parameters and apply custom constraints to control the final fiber architecture. The resulting fiber network geometry is imported into Abaqus CAE for meshing and analysis. Example of 3D models are presented to quantify the effect of misalignment randomness on the fiber compressive strength and are benchmarked against conventional micromodels with idealized uniaxial misalignment.

Beyond model generation, validation of the micromodels remains an important and unresolved issue. The strong sensitivity of the predicted fiber-direction compressive strength to geometric assumptions in the micromodels, as demonstrated in this work, reinforces the need for experimental verification. Recent validation efforts have employed in situ testing combined with ultra-high-resolution imaging techniques such as synchrotron X-ray computed tomography (CT) [10,11]. While these techniques offer valuable insight into damage mechanisms and may support model generation and validation, their reliance on very small specimens may raise concerns about the representativeness of observed failure modes. In addition, the high cost and limited availability of synchrotron facilities limit their broader accessibility.

To provide a more accessible validation pathway, this study considers a thin four-point bend notched specimen configuration. The test setup is designed to promote initiation and stable growth of localized fiber kinking while avoiding global buckling and can be implemented using a standard universal testing machine. The thickness of the specimen is reduced to one ply—approximately 180 microns—allowing the use of an embedded fiber-segmented micromodel that spans the entire width of the specimen and captures the full region where fiber kinking develops. A coarser, homogenized global finite element model is used to apply boundary conditions consistent with the experimental setup onto the embedded micromodel. This configuration enables direct comparison between experimental observations and numerical predictions, offering a promising route for verifying micromechanical simulations and advancing predictive capabilities for fiber-direction compressive strength.

2 MICROMODELS WITH IDEALIZED FIBER MISALIGNMENT

In this section, two-dimensional and three micromodels with idealized initial fiber misalignment are used to highlight some of the key challenges and limitations of micromodels for prediction of fiber kinking and fiber-direction compressive strength in CFRPs.

2.1 Finite Element Models

An idealized fiber misalignment is introduced in the FE models using a cosine function with a half-wavelength L and an initial misalignment angle ϕ_0 as illustrated in Figure 1 and defined by Equations (1) & (2).

Figure 1: Idealized fiber misalignment.

$$\begin{aligned}
 y &= -\frac{\lambda}{2} & \text{for } x \leq -\frac{L}{2} \\
 y &= -\frac{\lambda}{2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{L}\left(x + \frac{L}{2}\right)\right) & \text{for } -\frac{L}{2} < x < \frac{L}{2} \\
 y &= \frac{\lambda}{2} & \text{for } x \geq \frac{L}{2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here, λ is the amplitude of the misalignment curve, defined as:

$$\lambda = \frac{2L}{\pi} \tan(\phi_0) \tag{2}$$

The two-dimensional FE micromodel considered in this study is shown in Figure 2. The model consists of a rectangular fiber-segmented domain with dimensions $L_{tot} \times H$ analyzed using the Abaqus finite element software. A uniform fiber misalignment is imposed perpendicular to the loading direction by shifting the Y-coordinates of all nodes according to the cosine function described above. The model is partitioned into N fiber segments and $N + 1$ matrix segments. A fiber diameter of $5 \mu\text{m}$, representative of IM7 carbon fibers, is used to define the height of the fiber partitions while the matrix partition height is selected such that the fiber regions occupy a target area fraction of $V_f = 60\%$.

The model uses 2D plane strain quadrilateral elements (CPE4), with a unit thickness assumed in the out-of-plane direction. Abaqus built-in cohesive contact is used to model the mechanical interaction at the fiber–matrix interfaces. Boundary conditions include a fixed constraint in the axial (X) direction on one end of the model, with loading applied at the opposite end via a reference point and coupling constraints on the axial degree of freedom. A pinned condition is applied to the bottom-left corner node to prevent rigid body translation in the Y direction. Depending on the model dimensions, the total number of degrees of freedom ranged from approximately 50,000 to 150,000. The total model length selected was $L_{tot} = 200 \mu\text{m}$, with a nominal misalignment half wavelength of $L = 150 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 2: 2D FE micromodel

The three-dimensional FE model with idealized fiber misalignment is similar to the 2D model but incorporates a random distribution of cylindrical fibers within a $H \times W \times L_{tot}$ prismatic block of matrix, as shown in Figure 3. The model is generated by sweeping a 2D fiber-segmented cross-sectional mesh profile created using a modified Random Search Algorithm, enabling the generation of highly packed representative volume elements (RVEs). A fiber volume fraction of $V_f = 60\%$ is used in this study.

Similar to the 2D model, a uniaxial initial fiber misalignment is introduced in the 3D FE model by shifting (morphing) the mesh nodes along the transverse Z-direction. The mesh consists primarily of 8-node reduced-integration brick elements (C3D8R), with a smaller number of 6-node wedge elements (C3D6), resulting in a total degree of freedom count between 1.5 and 2.5 million. The nominal cross-sectional area of the 3D model is $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$, containing a total of 77 fibers. The mesh is generated using the Abaqus CAE Python scripting interface, with a minimum clearance of $0.25 \mu\text{m}$ imposed between fibers and with model boundaries to alleviate meshing difficulties and reduce excessive mesh refinements. A mesh refinement study determined that discretizing the fiber diameter with 16 elements along the circumference (element size $\approx 0.98 \mu\text{m}$) and 120 elements along the length in the axial loading direction (element size $\approx 1.6 \mu\text{m}$) was sufficient to achieve convergence of the peak load within 2%.

Figure 3: 3D FE micromodel.

The IM7/8552 carbon fiber/epoxy matrix material system is selected in this study due to its widespread use in aerospace applications and the broad availability of material property data. A linear elastic orthotropic material model is used for the IM7 fiber material and the local fiber orientation within the segmented fiber regions in the mesh is assigned using Abaqus tools for surface-based discrete

orientation definition, allowing the material principal directions to follow both the initial misalignment geometry and its deformation during loading. The analysis accounts for nonlinear geometry effects. For the 8552 epoxy matrix, a nonlinear plasticity-based material model is adopted, using the extended Drucker–Prager formulation available in Abaqus material models library for modeling concrete damage plasticity. The fiber–matrix interface is modeled using a cohesive contact formulation, including a bilinear traction–separation law with a quadratic damage initiation criterion and a mixed-mode, energy-based Benzeggagh–Kenane (BK) law for damage evolution. The material properties used for the IM7/8552 system are obtained from the literature [6,12].

2.2 Analysis Results

Under compressive loading, shear stresses develop in regions of fiber misalignment, leading to local fiber rotation and a further increase in matrix shear stresses as well as matrix/fiber interfacial stresses. As compressive loading continues to increase, this results in matrix yielding and/or interfacial debonding, ultimately leading to the formation of a kink band, as illustrated in Figure 4 for a 2D model.

Figure 4. Kink band formation in a 2D micromodel with uniform sine curve fiber misalignment under compressive loading.

To capture the snap-back instability associated with kink band formation, the Abaqus Riks implicit solver is used for the analysis of the 2D model. Figure 5 shows an example of typical load-displacement response (normalized into a stress-strain response) with snap-back instability obtained in the 2D model with the Riks solver for an initial misalignment angle of 2 degrees.

Figure 5: Typical load–displacement response for 2D (Riks) and 3D (Explicit) models showing snap-back instability.

For the 3D model, analysis is performed using the explicit dynamic solver under an applied displacement and quasi-static loading conditions. The use of mass scaling enables a computationally efficient simulation, with total simulation times ranging from 2 to 4 hours on a 60-core machine for the 3D models considered in this study, which contain between 1.5 and 3 million degrees of freedom. For comparison, an analysis of a 3D model with 1.5 million degrees of freedom required approximately 12 hours to reach the peak load using the Riks implicit solver on the same machine. It is worth noting that while the explicit solver can accurately capture the peak load prior to instability, it cannot resolve the post-peak response due to the onset of dynamic effects and loss of equilibrium. Figure 6a shows the development of plastic strain in the confined matrix regions between fibers in the area of misalignment just before instability, and Figure 6b illustrates the progression of interfacial damage. For the IM7/8552 material properties used in this study, the instability is initiated by matrix yielding, which occurs prior to full fiber–matrix debonding. Lower interfacial shear strength properties may lead to an instability mechanism dominated by interfacial debonding.

The typical load–displacement response for a 3D model analyzed with the explicit solver is compared to that of a 2D model analyzed using the implicit *Riks* solver in Figure 5.

Figure 6: (a) Plastic strain localization and (b) interfacial damage near fiber misalignment prior to instability in the 3D model.

As documented in the literature, the compressive strength predicted by the typical micromodels presented above is highly sensitive to a range of parameters. These include material input properties—such as the matrix yield strength and interfacial shear strength—as well as geometric characteristics, such as the initial fiber misalignment angle and the wavelength of the sine function used to represent the misalignment. Additional challenges arise from the sensitivity of the results to model size and boundary conditions. The dependence on geometry, model size and boundary conditions particularly complicates the development of a robust model for prediction of the fiber-direction compressive strength.

For illustration purposes, the effects of some selected parameters on the load-displacement obtained with the 2D model using the Riks solver are presented in Figures 7 and 8 below.

Figure 7: Effect of the misalignment angle in the 2D model: a) stress-strain response and b) compressive strength as a function of misalignment angle Φ_0 .

Figure 8: Effect of number of fibers in the 2D model: a) stress-strain response and b) compressive strength as a function of the number of fibers (H dimension in Figure 2).

Figure 7 shows the effect of the initial misalignment angle Φ_0 on the compressive strength, calculated as the peak load divided by the cross-sectional area. In these models, the number of fibers—corresponding to the height dimension H in Figure 2—was set to 50. As shown, the compressive strength is highly sensitive to small misalignment angles in the range of 1° to 3° , and it decreases as the misalignment increases, which is a well-known behavior. For reference, a 0° compressive strength X_c of 1540 MPa is reported for IM7/8552 in the Hexcel datasheet [13], which corresponds to a misalignment angle of approximately 1.8° in the model.

Figure 8 illustrates the effect of the number of fibers (i.e., the model height H) on the compressive response. As shown, the compressive strength increases with the number of fibers and appears to converge for values above 60 fibers. In these simulations, a misalignment angle of 1° was used.

Similar dependencies are observed using the 3D micromodel presented in Figure 3.

3 MICROMODELS WITH RANDOM FIBER MISALIGNMENT

The results presented above underscore the strong sensitivity of the compressive strength predicted using micromodels to the geometric characteristics of the fiber misalignment introduced. In these models, the misalignment is idealized as uniform and uniaxial—an assumption that does not accurately reflect the inherently stochastic nature of fiber misalignment observed in real composite materials. Moreover, the common implementation approach, which involves uniformly shifting the entire volume—including both fibers and matrix—according to a prescribed misalignment function, may undermine the validity of applying periodic boundary conditions. Periodic boundary conditions are often used to reduce mesh size sensitivity and ensure representative behavior in the homogenization of RVE results.

3.1 Model Generation

One of the reasons simplified misalignment is typically adopted in micromodels is that generating highly packed representative cells with a stochastic distribution of non-intersecting fibers and spatially varying 3D misalignment poses a significant geometric and meshing challenge. To address this, a novel method based on a computer graphics modeling engine is proposed in this work. The method uses open-source computer graphics software Blender to construct complex and realistic fiber architectures.

The overall workflow for the method is outlined in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Workflow for generating realistic 3D fiber architectures in FE micromodels using Blender.

The process begins by creating a Blender scene that includes N randomly positioned fibers confined within a container box (Figure 9a). The container is typically modeled as a rectangular prism to facilitate the application of periodic boundary conditions in the FE model, but other shapes, such as a cylinder, can also be used. The number of fibers N is selected such that the total fiber volume matches a target volume fraction V_f relative to the container volume. Individual fibers may be randomly selected from a pre-defined collection with varying geometric characteristics, such as differences in diameter and local misalignment (undulation with wavelength smaller than the length of the container). Random rotations along all three Euler angles can also be applied to further randomize the initial positioning and include global fiber misalignment. Each fiber is modeled as a cylindrical mesh with user-defined discretization in the axial and radial directions.

The initial fiber distribution is generated using an emitter plane and Blender's hair particle system modifier. At this stage, many fibers typically intersect, as illustrated in Figure 9a. If no intersections are present, which may occur for very low fiber volume fraction, the Repulsion Simulation step b) can be skipped and the process can continue at step c). Otherwise, to remove intersections and achieve a tightly packed configuration, Blender's rigid body physics simulation engine is used.

Each fiber is assigned an active rigid body model with collision detection enabled, while the container is defined as a passive rigid body, also with collision enabled. Gravity is disabled in the simulation, and Blender's default repulsion force field is applied to all active rigid bodies (fibers). This force is proportional to the overlapping volume between intersecting objects. This setup causes overlapping fibers to repel one another at the start of the simulation, triggering collisions with neighboring fibers and the container walls. The system then evolves toward an equilibrium state in which no fibers intersect either each other or the container boundaries (Figure 9b). Surface friction and damping may be introduced to control the time needed to reach equilibrium. The final distribution and orientation of the fibers may exhibit stochastic behavior due to the combined influence of the repulsion force model, collision dynamics, and multi-body interactions. While evaluation of this stochastic behavior is beyond the scope of the present work, it is identified as a subject of future investigation.

Once equilibrium is reached, the simulation is baked, and the vertex coordinates of each fiber mesh are extracted. These coordinates are imported into Abaqus CAE, where they are used to reconstruct each fiber geometry via a series of spline profiles extruded along the fiber axis (Figure 8c). A lofted surface is generated from the spline sections and capped to create solid fiber volumes. The fiber volumes are then used to cut into a prismatic matrix block using Abaqus CAE's native Boolean operations, resulting in the final fiber and matrix volume geometry (Figure 9d).

Meshing of the fiber and matrix domains is then carried out using Abaqus CAE's meshing tools (Figure 9e). The fibers can typically be meshed using a sweep technique, enabling the generation of high-quality hexahedral or hex-dominated elements. For the matrix, sweep or bottom-up meshing strategies may be feasible when the fiber paths are relatively straight or when the fiber volume fraction is low. However, in the general case—particularly when dealing with random 3D fiber misalignment and high fiber volume fractions—free tetrahedral meshing is required to ensure successful mesh generation.

The entire process is automated by leveraging Blender and Abaqus CAE respective Python interfaces. It is worth noting that the Blender simulation is typically very fast. In this work, the 3D random positioning problem involving up to 800 fibers was resolved in under one minute.

Figures 10 and 11 present examples of fiber distributions generated with a 60% fiber volume fraction and approximately 500 fibers. Figure 10 illustrates a case in which a small degree of global fiber misalignment was introduced by allowing fiber rotation during the collision simulation. Figure 10a shows the initial fiber distribution in the Blender scene, while Figure 10b shows the final configuration after the repulsion-based collision simulation. Figure 10c provides a 3D view of the final distribution.

In the front view shown in Figure 10b, darker regions correspond to misaligned fibers. Clustering of these fibers appears in two distinct regions, suggesting a possible underlying stochastic behavior associated with the collision physics and multi-body dynamics of the packing process.

Figure 10: Example of 3D fiber distribution with global misalignment: a) initial distribution (2D view), b) final distribution in 2D view, and c) final distribution in 3D view.

Figure 11 presents an example of a fiber distribution in which a few individual fibers exhibit large global misalignment angles approaching 45° . This configuration is intended to mimic observations from CT scans of carbon/epoxy specimens where significant fiber misalignment occurred at ply interfaces due to the manufacturing process. The initial and final fiber distributions in the Blender model are shown in Figures 11a and 11b, respectively. Figure 11c shows CT data highlighting individual fibers with large misalignment angles.

Figure 11: Example of simulated fiber distribution with large global misalignment angles: a) initial distribution, b) final distribution and c) similar fiber distribution observed in CT data.

Rigid body constraints can be applied to individual fibers to provide additional control over their final distribution. In the example shown in Figure 12, identical fibers with initial uniaxial sine-curve misalignment along the Z-axis, defined by Equation 1, are used in the repulsion-based simulation. Rigid body constraints are introduced to restrict fiber motion to translations along the Y and Z directions during the simulation, with no rotations allowed. This results in a random, non-intersecting fiber distribution with uniform uniaxial fiber misalignment, similar to the configuration shown in Figure 3. However, a key distinction is that the matrix block in Figure 12 remains a regular, undeformed rectangular prism, whereas in Figure 3, the matrix geometry is morphed to follow the fiber paths. Maintaining a prismatic matrix block in this case would enable straightforward and unambiguous application of periodic boundary conditions.

In Figure 13, the same rigid body constraints are applied, and the same fiber geometry with sine-curve misalignment is used. However, each fiber is randomly sampled from a collection of fibers that have been pre-rotated (randomly) about the X-axis. This introduces variation in the orientation of the local misalignment plane, resulting in a non-intersecting fiber distribution with randomly oriented sine-curve misalignment, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Random distribution of fibers with uniform uniaxial sine-curve misalignment.

Figure 13: Random fiber distribution with sine-curve misalignment randomly rotated about the X-axis.

3.2 Analysis Results

Analysis results are presented and compared for the four 3D micromodels listed in Table 1, which outlines the key features of each configuration. All models incorporate local fiber misalignment using the sine curve function defined in Equation 1, centered at mid-length $L_{tot}/2$, with parameters $L = 150 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Phi_0 = 1^\circ$. Each model contains 77 fibers, corresponding to a fiber volume fraction of 60%.

The primary differences among the models lie in the orientation of the misalignment plane along the X-axis (uniaxial vs. randomly rotated) and the method used to introduce the misalignment, which affects the external geometry of the matrix volume. Model 1 uses the traditional “morphing” approach discussed in Section 2, where the mesh is deformed to follow the uniaxial sine curve. Models 2 through 4 are generated using the Blender-based approach described above, which allows for maintaining an undeformed prismatic or cylindrical matrix block. The orientation of the misalignment plane is uniaxial in Models 1 and 2 (along the XZ plane) and randomly rotated along the X axis in Models 3 and 4. Additionally, Model 4 features a cylindrical cross section, unlike the rectangular cross sections used in Models 1–3. All models use similar boundary conditions to those shown in Figure 2, and the simulations are performed using the explicit solver under quasi-static compressive displacement loading in the X direction.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Matrix Cross Section</i>				
<i>Iso View</i>				
<i>Features</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uniform fiber misalignment in XZ plane - Rectangular cross section - Mesh morphed to misalignment sine curve in XZ plane 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uniform fiber misalignment in XZ plane - Rectangular cross section - Prismatic mesh aligned along X 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Random rotation of fiber misalignment plane along X - Circular cross section - Prismatic mesh aligned along X 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Random rotation of fiber misalignment plane along X - Circular cross section - Cylindrical mesh aligned along X

Table 1: 3D micromodel configurations with varying misalignment orientation and matrix geometry.

The stress-strain response (normalized load-displacement response) for the four configurations is plotted and compared in Figure 14. The respective compressive strength values are listed in Table 2.

Figure 14: Effect of number of fibers on the compressive strength in the 2D model.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
X_c [MPa]	1440	1672	2404	2627

Table 2: Compressive strength values for the four 3D micromodel configurations.

A significant variation in compressive strength is observed across the different configurations, with an 80% increase between the lowest value of 1440 MPa for Model 1 and the highest value of 2627 MPa for Model 4. The substantial increase in average compressive strength observed in Models 3 and 4, compared to Models 1 and 2, can be physically justified: the random orientation of fiber misalignment delays the early development of shear stress along a preferred direction. In contrast, Models 1 and 2—with their uniaxial misalignment—promote early localization of matrix shear along the XZ plane. In Models 3 and 4, a global direction of matrix shearing eventually becomes dominant under continued compressive loading, ultimately leading to instability. Figure 15 illustrates the global shearing deformation observed in Model 3 just prior to failure, characterized by a combination of torsion about the X-axis and bending in the XZ plane.

Figure 15: a) Combined torsion and bending deformation and b) development of plastic strains prior to failure in Model 3 (deformation scale is multiplied by 2).

The differences in peak load between Models 1 and 2, and between Models 3 and 4, are also notable, highlighting the influence of the cell geometry on the predicted compressive strength. This sensitivity remains a challenge for predicting the fiber-direction compressive strength of CFRPs using micromechanics modeling. Ideally, micromodel predictions using representative volume elements (RVEs) should be independent of model size and shape. Ongoing work includes the implementation of periodic boundary conditions to evaluate whether such an approach can mitigate these model dependencies.

4 THIN FOUR-POINT BEND NOTCHED SPECIMEN

The results presented in the previous sections highlight the need for direct experimental validation of micromodels for predicting fiber-direction compressive strength. To support this need, a thin four-point bend notched specimen configuration is considered. The configuration is designed to facilitate localized kinking in the notch region while avoiding global buckling. The thickness of the specimen is reduced to the minimum (one ply, or about 180 microns thick), allowing for the use of an embedded fiber-segmented micromodel directly in the notched region. This enables direct comparison between simulation and experimental results.

The test setup is illustrated in Figure 17 and includes a Plexiglas fixture that enables the observation of failure and full-field strain monitoring using the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique, while also preventing global buckling. Figure 17a shows an example of the DIC-measured axial strain distribution prior to failure initiation, and Figure 17b shows the out-of-plane kink band failure that developed from the notch, as visible in post-test CT data. The load-displacement responses obtained for six one-ply thick IM7/8852 specimens are shown in Figure 18. A load drop in the load-displacement response was associated with the initial kinking failure at the tip of the notch. After initiation, the kink band continued to grow in a stable manner along the transverse direction.

Figure 16. Four-point bend test setup.

Figure 17. a) Example of DIC-measured axial strain field prior to failure initiation, and b) out-of-plane kinking failure visible in CT data.

Figure 18. Load-displacement results for six IM7/8552 notched specimens.

The finite element model developed for comparison with experimental data is shown in Figure 19. A coarser homogenized global FE model is used to impose boundary conditions representative of the experiment, while the entire notch region where kinking develops is modeled using an embedded fiber-segmented local micromodel. This approach eliminates the ambiguities commonly associated with RVE size and boundary condition assumptions. Analysis and comparison with experimental data are ongoing at the time of writing.

Figure 19. Embedded local and global Abaqus FE model for the Thin Four-Point Bend Specimen.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This work introduced a novel methodology for generating realistic 3D micromodels of CFRPs with random fiber misalignment for predicting fiber-direction compressive failure. A key contribution is the introduction of a computer graphics-based modeling framework using the open-source software Blender that enables the efficient creation of densely packed fiber architectures with spatially varying, stochastic misalignment. This approach addresses the limitations of conventional micromodels based on uniaxial sine-wave misalignment, which do not capture the true variability of fiber architectures in CFRPs and may lead to overly conservative strength predictions. It is also worth mentioning that the misalignment amplitude in such idealized micromodels is typically a calibrated parameter, further limiting their predictive capability.

Finite element simulations showed that both the orientation of fiber misalignment and the geometry of the representative domain can have a significant influence on the predicted compressive strength. Models incorporating randomly rotated misalignment planes led to delayed shear localization and a substantial increase in predicted strength—by as much as 80%—compared to conventional micromodels models with uniaxial misalignment. These results underscore the importance of accurately representing fiber architecture variability to enhance the reliability of micromechanical predictions.

To address the critical challenge of experimental validation, a thin four-point bend notched specimen was proposed. This configuration promotes localized kink band development while preventing global buckling. The small thickness of the specimen enables the use of a high-fidelity embedded fiber-segmented micromodel directly in the notched region for micromechanics-based simulation of fiber kinking. Preliminary test results confirmed the specimen's suitability for studying fiber-direction compressive failure through fiber kinking, laying the groundwork for direct validation.

Future work will focus on implementing periodic boundary conditions to reduce size and boundary effects and on validation using the proposed specimen configuration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was partially funded by the U.S. Government under Agreement No. W911W6-17-2-0002. Such support is gratefully acknowledged. The U.S. Government technical monitor is Mahendra Bhagwat. The views and conclusions contained in this document are those of the authors and should not be interpreted as representing the official policies, either expressed or implied, of the U.S. Government.

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